

A PHENOMENOLOGICAL INTERPRETATION OF THE PHAEDRA COMPLEX

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ABSTRACT

This article addresses the theme 'The Phaedra Complex'. Its scientific relevance lies in the fact that it contributes to the enrichment of scientific annals about the phenomena that affect human beings in their bonds of affection and development of psychosexuality, both in childhood and adulthood. Its social relevance lies in the scope of clarifying to the lay public that the most varied desires are part of human life and can manifest themselves in different directions without there being a loss of the sense of character and virtue, since many of these manifestations are outside the sphere of individual conscious control. This is a bibliographical, descriptive and explanatory research. The objective is to deepen studies on the subject and expand knowledge about the functioning of the human psyche. The Phaedra complex is a subject little studied by the psychoanalytic community, treated as a manifestation of desire of a generally obsessive and neuropathic nature of the stepmother for her stepson. Phaedra's passion for the young Hippolytus is something that goes beyond the limits of erotic desire; it is a cathartic expression of the ego dominated by the Oedipus Complex, in which the barrier of phylogenetic prohibition imposed by incest does not exist, and the path is free to advance on a terrain that proves to be fruitful, because between them a relationship of affection and care precedes. This feeling is the product of the latent mnemonic action that does the work of inverting the latent libidinal desire in relation to the unattained object and when the lines cross at a certain moment in time it erupts with enormous violence, not allowing a conjunctural analysis of the facts, which ends in a neurotic manifestation on the part of those involved, since public opinion and social sanctions will weigh on their shoulders. It is observed that there was a phenomenal inversion of values and expectations: Theseus saw in Phaedra the image of his adolescent passion, Ariadne; but the young woman saw an old man, no longer the young and charming warrior with whom she had fallen in love; However, when she saw Hippolytus, she imagined she was seeing the Love of her memory.

Keywords: Phaedra complex. Theseus. Hippolytus. Obsessive-compulsive neurosis. Female sexuality.

INTRODUCTION

Human life is marked by a wide variety of feelings, ranging from the simplest and most understandable to the most complex, which require deeper study and are sometimes more difficult to comprehend due to the social values attached to them. This occurs from birth to death. Some feelings are accepted by society, while others are not, which does not prevent them from occurring, since human beings do not possess sufficient power to control psychic forces they are unaware of; it is up to each party involved in the process to keep them secret or reveal them to others, even knowing the risks involved in doing so.

Classical Greek literature provided Sigmund with elements that allowed him to identify the *Oedipus Complex*, a moment in childhood when a child is overcome with love for their mother or father, depending on the mother's sex, without realizing it because, at this stage, their brain is still immature and not developed enough to determine and direct their thoughts. Similarly, Greek tragic literature offered elements to identify the *Phaedra Complex*, a phenomenological process of a loving nature that occurs to a greater degree on the part of the stepmother towards her stepson, the highlighted expression being emphasized because it can also occur from the mother towards her son, albeit less explicitly, because it is protected by the social construction of unconditional maternal love.

Its complexity lies in the fact that this passion occurs when the stepson is already in the final period of puberty/beginning of adolescence, that is, he is already a man, with reasonable control over his emotions. This complex is the product of a repressed passion that cannot be consolidated, remaining therefore latent and in a state of unsatisfied desire and, once unfulfilled, it only needs to find its directional object to explode uncontrollably, precisely because it is weighed down by an affective-moral issue, not a legal restriction, as happens with the mother-son relationship.

The first known account, which gave the complex its name, is that of Phaedra and her stepson Hippolytus, a classic tale that was transformed into a tragic play by Euripides (485/84 BC-406 BC), performed in the Athens theater in 428 BC. The tragic author described psychic processes such as obsession, paranoia, *voyeurism*, epilepsy, and dementia with such clarity that it is captivating and impressive [*and even, in some cases, anticipating*] the [*supposed*] discoveries of contemporary Psychiatry. He showed how men were governed by an imperious and invisible force, capable of driving them to extremes, surpassing the aesthetic and moral values of an era. He exposes the intrinsic world of the characters [*so clearly*] as if it were possible to completely strip it bare, and their deepest, uncontrollable spirits and feelings could

be unveiled to the public. The character was stripped of his mask. Thus, to claim that he is the first psychologist is a worthy approach, since he demonstrated this in the theater [*before laypeople*]. what Charcot would later show more than two thousand years later at the Salpêtrière [*to an audience of incredulous scholars*] And Freud masterfully corroborated this with the creation of Psychoanalysis, proving that the last of the great tragic poets of Athens was right about the human psyche and its behavior.

Phaedra was one of Euripides' main heroines, later represented in plays by Seneca (3 BC-65 AD) in 54 AD and by Racine (1639-1699) in 1776. The Phaedra Complex is a feeling of immense violence because it occurs between an adult and another adult, which overshadows the possibilities of fulfilling a previously latent desire. Furthermore, it is a manifestation of an unresolved Oedipus Complex, which includes a complete digression regarding the phylogenetic guilt of incest, possibly involving a feeling of guilt in relation to the affective bonds that link those involved in the love triangle.

This is an empirical manifestation, in which an entire ontogenetic construction is present when the case is analyzed with due technical accuracy, revealing traces of mnemonic passion that was not psychologically compensated; understanding by this expression that the characterizing element of the impediment to the amorous direction did not exist, that is, the Oedipal manifestation occurred towards an individual without blood ties to her, in other words, the stepmother in love with her stepson is loving a younger version of the father, the same one she was prevented from loving as a child and who now sees herself in the possibility of doing so.

In the same interpretative proportion attributed to the Oedipus Complex, the Phaedra Complex is an anthropological component, that is, it is something inherent to human phenomenological existence, with the difference that the former manifests itself in early childhood, with a revival occurring at the beginning of adolescence, and the latter only happens in adulthood, when it is presumed that feelings arising from impulses should represent an object of control on the part of the individual. This clarifies that society knows it exists; however, it does not recognize it as something plausible for acceptance.

THE PHAEDRA COMPLEX

The Phaedra Complex refers to a classic pathological attraction between stepmother and stepson; a counterpart to the Oedipal relationship, observed more frequently as a consequence of the ever-increasing rates of divorce and remarriage. However, this amorous feeling is not

generically and spontaneously characterized, motivated simply by the absence of blood ties uniting the parties; because what arises between those involved [*or from a single party*] is a true *pathos*, a broad, profound feeling and an uncontrollable desire to possess the beloved object. It originates from the classic tales and stories of the Greeks and gained space in the theater, which allowed it to reach modern times with greater force. In tragic theater, it has two versions, one repudiated by the public because Phaedra, the passionate stepmother, reveals her love and her plan to conspire against the king, her husband and the father of her object of desire, to her stepson. The second version, the one that has reached modern times, is a nurse who takes the news to Hippolytus, who rejects the idea, which is then passed on to the young woman. After the boy's rejection, Fedra falls into despair and, consequently, into a terrible paranoid depression, eventually becoming emaciated, until, unable to fight against that unrequited love, coupled with her psychotic delusions due to her physical weakness, she commits suicide.

Phaedra's passion for the young Hippolytus transcends the limits of erotic desire; it is a cathartic expression of the ego dominated by the Oedipus complex, where the phylogenetic barrier of incest is absent, leaving a clear path to advance into fertile ground, because a relationship of affection and tenderness precedes them.

Having explained that this is an Oedipal manifestation, not sublimated, what we have is that this object desire remained latent and so distinct that it knew how to analyze the exact moment to realize it. The point of clarification is that, in the phase of the occurrence of the feeling of possession of the father or the object of love that could have replaced him, there was an affective construction that made its emergence possible. The drama occurred at the moment of the dissolution of the forbidden feeling, in which it became even more concentrated, perhaps provoked by some situation that was beyond the child's control. In this, we arrive at a broader understanding of the Phaedra Complex, which can be interpreted as an attempt to compensate for the feeling of insecurity that the forced separation provoked in her ego; that is, the woman possesses an infantilized ego, not matured in relation to her object of love, in such a way that she confuses it with an object of possession.

This is what happens to Phaedra, who does not see her stepson as someone she loves, but as someone who belongs to her by right, and for this reason, she needs him to accept her as his own and not only her love, an object she offers him as a disguise. When she sees her love rejected by her stepson, she falls into despair because she finds herself in a situation of imminent danger, unprotected against the monster that can devour her, just as happened when she was only a defenseless child, and paradoxically, she never ceased to be one.

Applying this same interpretative principle to stepmothers infatuated with their stepchildren, what we have is a condition of revival of a childish *pathos* that, for some unknown reason, cannot be sublimated, remaining so intense that even after many years it presents itself under the same yearning of obsessive violence, controlling the dynamics of the situation that seems like a mere existential twilight. The problem is that even this happiness that the lover emphasizes feeling is *pathological*; not because she maintains a passion that, in social terms, may seem forbidden and even considered as such; but precisely because the one who feels it has no control whatsoever over her feelings, being capable of going to extremes to satisfy her intense desire determined by her egodystonic nature.

This demonstrates that its occurrence has its psychic roots, grounded in a childlike stage of human development in which the woman in question, still a child, was subjected to strong emotional tensions and found in the represented adult figure a phallic substitute for the father to whom she directed her Oedipal drive, desiring to achieve a fusional state with him, not driven by an erotic desire, but as a way to protect herself from an intense and devouring evil.

The Phaedra Complex applies primarily to stepmothers in relation to their stepchildren; however, it can also be applied to mothers, with the difference that a [*biological*] mother would not allow her passion for her son to go to extremes because of social sanctions that abhor incest; but, in the paternal unconscious, it wreaks monstrous havoc, with genuine feelings of jealousy and irrational hatred against the son. For this to occur, the woman must have the image of her beloved at the time of his marriage in a latent state in her unconscious memory. This image of the strong, vigorous, and young man is that of the husband on the 'day' of his wedding, which, surviving in a latent state, is awakened by the son when he reaches the age of his father, repressed in the maternal unconscious, and highlighted in the form of a drive, controllable only by the superego (extremely rigid social rules).

The issue of the observable occurrence of the Phaedra complex being taken to its ultimate consequences between stepmother and stepson, and not between mother and son, is that the former is under a state of ego-dystonicity, where an Idic drive dictates that this is how it should proceed, at the risk of continuing to be haunted by a fear that has plagued her since its occurrence. This is different for the mother, who retains, in relation to her husband, an aesthetic memory, less violent and easier to control the *pathos* that develops between them, in which, generally, there is the presence of the superego, represented in the figure of the father, which distances the mother from the son and even from the manifestation of her Oedipal love.

In the case of the stepmother, a situation arose in which her egoic satisfaction was prevented; however, it was not directed towards an object that could help dissolve the Oedipus

complex, which left her fixated in that phase and with a mnemonic fixation on her libidinal love target. Even though this condition is also observable in women who do not suffer from this neurosis, the fact is that they seek a similar figure, unlike what happens in the cases studied here, where the search is for an identical figure. And, in this search, anything goes to satisfy an egodystonic individual, even because those who possess this type of misunderstood construction about their own personality end up becoming obsessive, given the emotional fragility that consumes them in their thoughts about things and everything around them. It is a very delicate situation that must be analyzed with extreme rigor and care, even because treatment is not reduced to superficial interventions or threats of sanctions that exceed reasonable limits.

The character who gave rise to the study of the problem, Phaedra, prominent in the work of Euripides and also in mythology, desires possession of her stepson as an object that belongs to her by divine right and, when analyzed in detail regarding the evolutionary behavior of the passion that leads to the pathological feeling itself, it is found that, first, the stepmother takes on a longing in relation to the object of love that is fueled by voyeurism, in which she loses herself observing, from a distance, her beloved, without him seeing her or even realizing that he is the object of platonic admiration.

However, since this is someone with egodystonic personality disorder, this condition does not satisfy her sufficiently, and her emotionally distorted ego yearns for much more, desiring possession of her beloved, as if she could thus merge with him, making him an intrinsic part of herself. This may seem, at first glance, like an erotic sexual desire; but it goes far beyond that and is an unknown way of finding a state of equilibrium for the irrational fear that has consumed her since childhood. By acting in this way, it is as if she could prevent her protector *from leaving*, understanding that, in childhood thinking, the expression "leaving" means "dying"; that is, she seeks, in a way she cannot comprehend, to make her object of passion live eternally within her.

In the final stage of the Phaedra complex's manifestation, guilt consumes the victim, because this is what becomes part of their own ego-dystonic state, where paranoia begins to consume them, overwhelmed by the fear of being punished by someone with the power to do so, in this case, the father. This contrasts with the Oedipus complex, where the girl fears being violated by her mother's hatred. This reveals an ontogenetic occurrence, that is, a revival of a psychological situation that occurred and was meant to be natural for the child but was not, due to some external factor, causing trauma. This led to the emergence of a fragile ego, which,

finding the appropriate situation, manifests itself in a direction contrary to what nature developed as an aspect of personological normality.

In Phaedra's case, history would leave us with a void, an unsolvable challenge for the analyst and the historian, had she not known Theseus in her youth. This same embarrassment occurs with Don Quixote when some theorists claim that Alonso Quijano never saw or knew Dulcinea del Toboso. Not having known her, there would have been no way he could have created even a pseudonym for her and preserved in his memory the image of such beauty. Even the most fervent delirium must obey certain patterns of development... In a way, we must bow to Aristotle of Stagira when he states that all intelligence passes through the senses... Paraphrasing this author, one can affirm that 'even the most deranged madness [*necessarily*] passes through the senses.'

Both the mentally ill individual and the one whose thoughts are in perfect working order will experience the same cognitive experiences; the way each one decodes the actions internalized through the senses determines whether they are a nervous patient or a normal being. This is one of the main precepts defended by Carl Gustav Jung (1875-1961) and is based on decades of clinical observations.

It is always very difficult to determine how experiences affect the feelings and thoughts of each individual, even because it is not known which of them occur in the intrapsychic world of each person. Everything suggests that the city of Crete, under the rule of King Minos, although very advanced in cultural terms, represented a place of terror, and horror had already taken control over all the inhabitants of that polis. Moreover, it was a kind of psychological terror, in which no one dared to rise up against the cruelty of the priest dominated by the most intense madness.

When Theseus appears, determined to exterminate the monster and put an end to that madness, he finds a path already trodden in this direction, with no one daring to undertake it. The fact that Minos' own daughter takes an active part in the undertaking already shows that there were others besides her who longed for an end; because, although there are no records to this effect, everything leads us to believe that young Cretans were also condemned to the labyrinth, and judging by Phaedra's attachment, even as a child, to the young hero, taking him as a neurotic lifeline, the pit was a recurring threat to children in any situation disapproved of by adults.

Regarding the character and her psychological disorder, Phaedra was a child when she left Crete and returned to it to marry her brother, already an adult; however, for the Greeks, the age at which a woman was considered eligible for marriage was seven years old. Therefore, she

returns before entering the latency phase, in which a sublimation of feelings of hatred, fear, and other situations that traverse childhood occurs during the manifestation of the Oedipus Complex. This situation could well help explain the confused feelings that tormented the thoughts of Euripides' heroine. The proposal she makes to Hippolytus is reminiscent of a scene already performed earlier, because her sister, Ariadne, begins to suffer convulsions, forcing Theseus to abandon her in favor of Dionysus—a strange situation to understand, coming from the hero, who was not accustomed to obeying the designs of any god.

Following this line of thought about Phaedra, we see that she expected to have her stepson's support in the undertaking, which did not happen, and, desolate, she took the shortest path to revenge and an honorable life. Judging by the age at which she was taken in marriage by Theseus, we are talking about a very young woman, overwhelmed by confused feelings about her own existence and everything around her, and who had not yet had children. What this may interfere with in the analysis is that she was free to carry out any daring plan, since her descendants would not be punished.

Phaedra's return to Crete must have represented a new trauma for her, reliving all the situations of confronting fear and insecurity in relation to the labyrinth, even though the monster had been beheaded by the Heroic Savior. There was something very deep in the Heroine's feelings that made her no longer feel safe beside her former love; in fact, it proved not to be so, it was merely a mnemonic fixation that, once revived, caused the ruin even of a god, who punished an innocent without any pity.

Even though Euripides only presented the conflicted, passionate woman on stage, mythology allowed us to understand Phaedra's journey before becoming Theseus' wife, especially since the plays were constructed from tales featuring important figures in the nation's history. The great merit of the tragic actors was to provide profound arguments and compelling analyses of the lives of these heroes who remained present in tales, legends, and existential interpretations. It arrived in the theater relatively late, when Athens itself and all thought were already beginning to be influenced by the questioning of thinkers, giving rise to the condition of subjectivity.

When Theseus arrives in Crete and kills the monster that haunted the Trezenes, he brings Ariadne with him, and Phaedra comes along. It can be assumed that Phaedra was around four or five years old [*the age of development of the Oedipus complex*]. However, Ariadne is abandoned. On an island to be wed to Dionysus, young Phaedra finds Theseus all to herself. Her unconscious desire is fulfilled. However, this distresses her because she loved her older sister. The complex, developed somewhat differently, occurs with the girl: she loves her father

and hates her mother, or develops an ambivalent attitude towards her. This whole situation, with its violent loves and jealousies, with its inevitable conflicts and repressions, determines an enormous amount of psychic effort and tension that can give rise to endless emotional disorders.

It cannot be said that Phaedra was insane; such an argument would be demanding too much of such a strong character who was affected by a series of exceptionally complex factors; but that she suffered from a neurotic symptomatic set is a fact, judging by her behavior and the experiences she was subjected to from early childhood. The environment to which she was subjected was conducive to the appearance of profound psychic disorders, in which her mother falls in love with the royal bull, which already clarifies that the patron god of Crete was Poseidon, known for being an irascible, violent, and destructive god.

This situational description clarifies that she was born and lived, for a good part of her life, in a maddening environment, marked by violence and an exasperated fear of everything. It is not surprising that she became a strange figure, difficult to understand in terms of her behavior, ranging from extreme beauty to extreme wickedness when her most powerful desires were not satisfied. The desire to possess an imaginary Theseus leads her to an uncontrollable feeling towards Hippolytus, creating a love triangle in which one of the parties is completely disregarded and disconnected from the situation.

Phaedra came to live with her sister and brother-in-law because she didn't want to continue living with her tyrannical father. This clarifies that she met Theseus, the savior hero, when he was still young, slender, strong, and full of life, and consequently developed an overwhelming passion for him, which transformed into an Oedipus complex. When, years later, he asked her to marry him, she accepted under the illusion that he was her Oedipal Theseus. Thus, she created the perfect illusion of loving the man from her childhood Oedipal memories. But her dream ended the day she saw her stepson, who was nothing more than the visual representation of the Theseus she knew in her childhood, and then her Idic drive returned with uncontrollable force. Since she lacked any social sanction to prevent her from carrying out her intention, she was at the mercy of her childish desire, inflamed by an ego-dystonic drive. This sanction would be the cause of incest, which was harshly repressed by religion and law in those times. Religion prohibited incest between parents and children; but it said nothing regarding non-blood ties.

This is the great question regarding the Phaedra Complex, in which there seems to be a trio, as occurs in the Oedipus Complex; but, in the latter case, it involves a child, someone who is still dependent on the target object to which they direct all their aversion, because of the control and power they exert over the object of love. In the former case, we are already talking

about an adult influencing an immature young person, in all affective and erotic aspects. Naturally, given the circumstances, they are not erotically interested in their stepmother while awake, since they respect and love their father, and are not capable of betraying him in such an abject way, uniting themselves with someone who plots under their roof against the one to whom they owe respect.

The Greek tale was so methodical in its approach that it made the behavior of both characters involved in the plot very transparent, respecting their respective psychological aspects of development. The description of evil is so meticulous that it recounts each stage of Phaedra's life and the conditions to which she was subjected until she succumbed to the weight of her neurosis, surrendering to death as an ultimate end in an attempt to have her object of love. Unable to love him in life, she would love him in the afterlife.

Phaedra knew very well how her husband would act, even in relation to their son. By leaving a note tucked between his fingers, she was already arousing curiosity and the exact moment when, upon seeing his body hanging and overcome with despair, he would utter some curse without thinking of the consequences that would follow. She was very intelligent and astute, a common trait in individuals who go through conflict in childhood and who depend on maturing prematurely in order to survive in a hostile world; regrettably, children subjected to this type of confrontation completely lose the ability to separate feelings because they develop a state of egodystonia; they cannot cope with the conflict that affects them, keeping it silent, out of control.

The Phaedra Complex is not a simple phenomenon to analyze because the woman who experiences it goes through three stages: voyeurism, obsession, and paranoia—feelings typical of those suffering from *obsessive-compulsive disorder*, described by Sigmund Freud in his work **Pre-Psychoanalytic Writings** as *obsessive-compulsive neurosis*. Phaedra first becomes consumed by voyeurism towards her stepson, to the point of having a temple built in honor of the goddess Aphrodite in Troezen, at a strategic point from where she could observe her stepson exercising without him seeing her or realizing he was being admired from a distance. This feeling stems from the fact that those who suffer from this condition find solace in themselves, not because they are selfish; it is something much deeper and more complex, since it involves the psychological representation of a child who is simply in an adult body.

After this phase, Phaedra is consumed by an obsessive neurotic desire for Hippolytus, to the point of proposing that they kill the king, her father, so that they can live their love together. This stage represents the same moment when the child, dominated by the desire to possess the Oedipal object, desires the death of the rival in possession of the disputed object, a

feeling that the conscious mind sublimates, given that the real intent is to eliminate the adversary in the erotic dispute. Rejected in her proposal, she enters a paranoid state of persecution marked by the fear that Theseus will discover her plans and attempt to take her life. In the case of the child, this same feeling of fear dominates her, so much so that nature created, immediately after the Oedipal phase, a developmental stage that Sigmund Freud came to call the *latency phase*, a period that manifests itself as if nothing that happened during the emotional hurricane of the previous phase had any relevance or even if it had never existed. However, the adult is no longer protected by this amnesic psychic condition, and similarly, feelings and death wishes against one of the parents have become a matter of personal and intimate concern, unlike what happens with Euripides' heroine. And it is this situation, in particular, that leads her to wither away and eventually die.

Obsession is a complex psychological disorder, both for those who suffer from it and for those who live with such people. There is no exact answer to what can generate it. Deep traumas that violently affect the immune-psychological system of individuals are usually the trigger for a series of emotional and behavioral symptoms. It is observed that it is not guilt that makes her enter an obsessive-paranoid state; but rather, the fear of repression that would come from her husband. Had she not revealed her intention to Hippolytus, her object of love, she could have lived with the guilt of emotional betrayal without it leading her to the extreme of hanging herself, unleashing all her anger on the young man, as if he were to blame for her unhealthy passion. Phaedra's attitude reveals hatred for having been rejected, which makes her seek blind and brutal revenge.

For Freud,

It is not accurate to say that obsessive neurotics, bowed down under the weight of excessive morality, are merely defending themselves from *psychic reality* and punishing themselves through impulses that were simply felt. Historical reality also plays a part in the matter. In childhood, they experienced these evil impulses in a pure and simple way and transformed them into acts to the extent that the impotence of childhood allowed. Each of these excessively virtuous individuals went through a period of wickedness in childhood—a phase of perversion that was a precursor and precondition for the later period of excessive morality. The analogy between primitive men and neurotics will thus be established much more fully if we assume that, in the first case as well, *psychic reality*—about which we have no doubt as to the form it took—coincided in the beginning with concrete reality, that is, that primitive men actually *did* what all the evidence shows they intended to do (FREUD, 2006, p. 102).

Based on Freud's words, one can infer that Phaedra, when she was still a child, admired Theseus during his long physical exercises, and it can be presumed that she harbored a latent

desire to possess him, a repressed passion that manifests itself at the very moment when all feasible conditions are presented to her. This suppressed love, which later reignites in relation to Hippolytus, is merely the return of a primitive feeling caused by a common situation.

As everything in Greek mythology follows a pattern of chance, despite the hand of the Fates being involved, this condition reveals that the possibility of the Phaedra Complex occurring in society is very remote; because it is not about moral vulnerability regarding the relationship between stepmother and stepson; there must be a conjunction of sociological and phenomenological factors that make the probability of this happening very limited. The succession of misfortunes in relation to this woman and her life, in particular, would have to be so great that it would connote a situation for which there is no plausible explanation.

The Phaedra complex forms, similarly to the Oedipus complex, around a love triangle, with the difference that it is not the son who desires possession of the mother and the death of the father, but the stepmother who desires to possess the son and eliminate the father from the equation. Thus, the father is always the element representing the superego; therefore, he is the one who must be overcome, since he is the one who prevents the fulfillment/satisfaction of the latent desire. A striking characteristic of this complex is that, even with the love triangle, the paternal figure is sidelined, as if irrelevant, even disposable, because the focus is on the absolute possession of the object of love. When Phaedra proposes to her stepson, for whom she was deeply in love, dominated by confused and dissonant feelings, that he attack his father—and it is necessary to clarify here the difference between husband and father—the former understood as someone to whom a social commitment is made, and the latter as the one who holds supreme authority and in whose presence everyone is subject to his power and rules. In his thoughts and desire for control, it was against the second that he was plotting, which Hippolytus considered to be what he interpreted and rejected, because even though he did not follow his father's gods, he admired him and would not know how to live without his power subjugating him.

Here is another problem of interpretation carried out by Phaedra in relation to her object of love, in which, upon seeing Hippolytus, she not only judged herself to be seeing a younger Theseus, in physical appearance, but also allowed herself to be seduced by the amalgamation that the young man possessed the strength, courage, and greed for power that had always represented the life and existence of her father, who, at first, proved that the King, her father, was weak and impotent and, upon defeating evil, plotted to seize the throne based on an innocent promise. In some strange way, Phaedra, who was aboard the ship that brought the now Hero and the condemned youths back home, knew how the King's defeat had been planned, so

that, with his death, Theseus, considered a bold and fearless warrior, would automatically be elevated to the position without any problem.

Phaedra, dominated by his ego, would do anything to achieve his goal, which went far beyond the desire to possess the throne, something he already had; this may have caused Hippolytus to doubt the true intentions of his stepmother. The idea of being possessed by a woman was terrifying for the young man, and the notion of ruling over others was also outside his plans, suggesting that the age difference between them was already significant, with the heroine being considerably older than him. For her, this was something that didn't matter, because her desire was motivated by a peculiar condition that couldn't be hastily explained, and it took a long time for Athenian society to understand her after her drama was staged in the theater.

As previously reported, the difficulty in analyzing and interpreting the historical figure Phaedra and his behavior, even to the point of approaching an understanding of the neurotic disorder known as the *Phaedra Complex*, stems from the fact that without a complete and thorough anamnesis of the patient, revealing their entire life history, it is impossible to know whether one is dealing with a symptom motivated by an aesthetic passion or whether one is facing a complex clinical case in which the solution is traversed by the attempt to resolve an emotional conflict caused by a trauma so profound that it has left the patient fixated on childhood, maintaining all their violent feelings and desires as insane as they are uncontrollable.

The Phaedra Complex and its Correlation with the Midlife Crisis

As already highlighted elsewhere in this essay, the *Phaedra Complex* is a very complex phenomenological occurrence that depends on a series of factors to manifest itself in its full libidinal drive and be consummated as a fact between stepmothers and stepchildren. This does not mean that its manifestation does not also occur between mothers and children. In marriage, when the man begins to age, the woman tends to distance herself erotically from her husband, share the bed, separate rooms, ask the children for help, and it is during this period that male neurosis often begins, which can be called the *midlife crisis*. Unconsciously, the husband begins to think that his wife no longer loves him, that she wants to abandon him, that she has a younger lover, and things of that nature. It is very natural for this complex to present itself in the forties for men, and there is nothing paranormal about it, that is, a pre-defined rule. The case unfolds as follows: a couple marries when the man is around twenty years old and the woman is eighteen.

According to Hellen Fischer (2006, p. 38), "most men and women around the world get married in their twenties." The first child is born approximately two years later, when the husband is already twenty-two years old, but he was the great passion of the wife at the time of the marriage, that is, when he was twenty years old. Time passes, the son grows very similar to his father, and when he enters his golden twenties he will be identical to the man his mother fell in love with and made sure to keep this mnemonic image in her unconscious. This son, whom she loves so much, is the reincarnation of her Cupid, who today is only restrained by the force of the superego. If this same complex repressed feeling occurs in men, it is less perceptible... perhaps because love in men is more violent and also shorter in duration, more ephemeral.

The paternal figure has always been closely linked to power, and a mystical aura has been lent to him, making him simultaneously necessary for a more brutal emotional control, unlike women, who were given the right to be more sensitive in this area.

Thus, this crisis was what happened to Phaedra in relation to Hippolytus, her stepson. Theseus remained alone for a long time after the death of his first wife, Hippolyta, the Amazon warrior whom he kidnapped during an adventurous journey, and during this period marked by loneliness and pain, he heard much about the charms of Phaedra, also a daughter of Minos and sister of Ariadne, the one who gave him the ball of thread and the sword so that he could kill the Minotaur and find his way out of the labyrinth. She was also the passion of his youth. Theseus hoped that Phaedra could compare to her sister. And, moved by this emotional impulse, they married. Indeed, she was so similar to Ariadne that Theseus felt himself once again in the bloom of youth (Spalding, 1974).

Phaedra, however, was not as good and faithful as her beautiful wife's allure suggested. The king's young son, Hippolytus, who was the same age as her, pleased her far more than her husband. When she first saw him, she imagined she was beholding her own husband rejuvenated, and the young man's beauty and innocence inflamed her heart to such an extent that she could not contain the impulse to fall in love with him. However, she concealed her passion deep within her heart. When Theseus made a journey to Troezen to visit his relatives and his son, she accompanied him. There too she tried to contain her passion, isolating herself from others and weeping over her sad fate in the shade of a myrtle tree. Informed of his stepmother's passion, Hippolytus listened to her with disdain, and his indignation grew when his stepmother, forgetting her duties, suggested that he overthrow his own father from the throne and share the royal scepter with her. In his indignation, young Hippolytus cursed all women

and imagined that the mere fact of having heard such a shameful suggestion was already a crime.

Phaedra no longer wanted to live after her proposal had been rejected. Deep inside, guilt and burning passion fought; but wickedness prevailed. Consumed by irrational hatred, she committed suicide. When Theseus returned, he found in his wife's stiff, clenched hand a letter she had written before dying: *"Hippolytus has attacked my honor, and I have only one way out. I prefer to die rather than be unfaithful to my husband."*

Theseus, impulsive as always, without questioning the young man, without giving him the opportunity to justify himself, expelled him from his country, not without first casting a deadly curse upon him, delivering him to the justice of Poseidon, his father. Impetuous as he was, the god of the sea fulfilled his son's wish, even knowing of his grandson's innocence. Only after his son's death did he learn that he was innocent of the guilt attributed to him by his stepmother.

The story recounts that Theseus, upon leaving Crete, brought Ariadne and Phaedra with him. Phaedra, who at the time would have been four or five years old, came to live with her sister and brother-in-law, as she did not want to continue living with her tyrannical father. This means that she met the hero when he was still young, slender, strong, and full of life, and consequently developed an Oedipus complex for him. When, years later, he asked her to marry him, she accepted under the illusion of him being the Oedipal Theseus. But her dream ended the day she saw her stepson, who was none other than the Theseus she had known in her childhood, and then her Idic impulse returned with uncontrollable force; and she had no social sanction to prevent her from carrying out her intention. This sanction would be the incestuous cause, which was harshly repressed by religion in those times. Religion prohibited incest between parents and children.

With age, sex becomes more mature, yet less frequent. Endocrinologists will say this is due to the lack of production or decrease in certain sex hormones; however, from a Darwinian and Freudian point of view, it is stated that every living being seeks the perpetuation of the species through sex. Therefore, as soon as a woman's reproductive life ends, which begins with menopause and the absence of menstruation, female libido tends to decline, and consequently, sexual desire. In this way, the woman enters a new phase of latency, dedicating herself to grandchildren, studies, and a subtle return to religion occurs, signifying a return to the father, something as if the adult woman were to relive unconscious infantile feelings, marked by some kind of psychological insecurity.

This clarification does not apply to the Phaedra complex, in which such feelings will occur according to a very specific and precise phenomenological characteristic, outlined in parameters where a traumatic event leads to the internalization of a strange and inexplicable *pathos* in an immediate way. When a causal link is established between the neurosis studied here and the *midlife crisis*, it is nothing more than a mechanism of study in which the feeling can be categorized as something related, a possible explanation for an occurrence that has already become phylogenetic for most couples.

What we intend to clarify here is that the psychological disorder discussed should not be entirely confused with a human situation so recurrent that it has become normal and can be resolved through understanding between the parties involved. The Phaedra Complex is a highly complex phenomenological expression, responding to a situation born and developed amidst a traumatic crisis, where the child is dominated by constant, persistent, and growing fear and awe, leading them to seek a neuropathic solution for their psychic coping.

CONCLUSION

The Phaedra Complex is a feeling of passion, derived from the Oedipus Complex, manifesting itself between stepmothers and stepchildren. It can also occur between mothers and children, and in fact, it usually does, but without the denotation of explicit sexual desire as happens with the former in relation to the latter. It can even have such a nature and come to a physical act when they are separated couples and/or the father is dead, which also requires that the mother have a very strong neurotic condition to the point of not recognizing the line that divides their worlds.

This feeling is a product of latent mnemonic action, which inverts the latent libidinal desire in relation to the unachieved object. When these lines intersect at a certain point in time, it erupts with enormous violence, preventing a contextual analysis of the facts, which ends in neurotic manifestations on the part of those involved, since public opinion and social sanctions will weigh heavily on their shoulders. It is observed that there was a phenomenal inversion of values and expectations: Theseus saw in Phaedra the image of his adolescent passion, Ariadne; but the young woman saw an old man, no longer the young and charming warrior with whom she had fallen in love; however, upon seeing Hippolytus, she imagined she was seeing the Love of her memory.

This conflict-ridden situation that marks the Phaedra Complex must have represented such a strange moment for the city of Athens and its spectators when the play was first presented

that it was only natural that it did not immediately win first place; it would take a long time to understand a feeling that, although it existed, had never been explored and highlighted until that moment. It's not that Euripides' genius wasn't recognized in his time; it was the depth of what he presented that startled everyone, as a novelty that would change social perception of human behavior and create a new way of analyzing, interpreting, and synthesizing human existence and its conscious and unconscious phenomenological manifestations.

Sociocultural repression limits not the appearance of this type of feeling, but its explicit manifestation; however, it is impossible for humans to fight against natural forces simply by saying that they do not exist or that they are not real, mere products of distorted thoughts in conflict with laws, rules, and social customs. Desires, once repressed, always seek an outlet and, if they do not find it in an adequate and harmonious way, they force and struggle until they manage to manifest themselves, whether for good or for bad. Before dying, the Stepmother seeks revenge against the one who rejected her and achieves it. Her object of desire is killed by the fury of Poseidon, who fulfills a request from his son, Theseus. Desire has been abolished, along with the one who desires and also the object of desire. Not the fact that the situation is a phenomenological representation of the twilight applied to human existence.

Just as all ancient history served as a foundation for the formation of the Greek man, this story also contributed to enabling a deeper and more dynamic understanding of some psychological symptoms that plague humanity and for which society lacks due comprehension. When the Phaedra Complex occurs between mother and son, it is very natural that this feeling falls upon the older child, since he was born during a period when the couple was madly in love. From a phylogenetic perspective, he is the one who carries within him all the pulsating and delirious passion that consumed the couple, and looking at him is like seeing all this youthful ardor ignite, feeling alive again, which reveals this to be a phenomenological issue, necessary to the human being as a species.

Phaedra suffers twice; once under the weight of her imagination, believing she sees in Hippolytus the figure of her mnemonic object of instinctual love. There was only his body; not his vigor, morals, or courage, and she knew this; however, dominated by a feeling over which she had no power, being under the influence of an ego-dystonic state, she surrenders to her madness and loses herself in it. Another time she suffered under the weight of reality, for she knew that this was not the man for whom she had nurtured so many illusions, and if Theseus, her husband, were to learn of her intentions regarding her stepson, he would execrate her.

Understanding the Phaedra Complex requires understanding the Oedipus Complex and its most intrinsic manifestations in children's thinking, conditions that are very well outlined

and clarified throughout the work of the Viennese Master. And, if by chance this particular condition did not occupy Sigmund's thoughts to the point of expressing his technical considerations, he read and studied the play, as well as the feelings and behavior presented by the characters in the plot, in such a way that in studies on obsessive neuroses he presents details that corroborate them.

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